

FOCCUS

Forecasting and observing the open-to-coastal ocean
for Copernicus users

D4.1

E-HYPE and LISFLOOD Preliminary Historical Model Dataset

Dataset

2025-05-28/version 3.0

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1. Executive Summary

This deliverable consists of preliminary outputs from the SMHI's E-HYPE and JRC's LISFLOOD+GREEN models for a historical time period. While the two approaches are similar in many ways, there are also some important differences. Here we describe only the major differences as they relate to the use of the available datasets. The detailed description of the both models' structure, set up, used data, calibration approach and particularities are provided in the deliverable **D4.2**.

Hydrological models aim to close the gap in the spatial or temporal extent of riverine observations, which are accurate but not widely available over larger areas. Moreover, coastal outlets are poorly covered with observations. Hydrological model systems can be integrated into forecasting chains, and provide predictions of river flows and transports to coastal zone forecasting systems across a range of time horizons, from short-term to seasonal predictions.

Both E-HYPE and LISFLOOD+GREEN models provide daily streamflow observations at European domains, however there are significant differences in their nutrients and sediment setups. The user of models' outflows depending on the goal can choose whether to use one of the model outputs or both as an ensemble.

The E-HYPE model simulates daily freshwater inflows, including nutrient and sediment concentrations and loads, from river outlets across all the European coastline. It is well suited where this fine time-resolution is needed for the coastal applications. As E-HYPE was recently overhauled with this version 4 update, the data provided here may have a lower accuracy than previously well calibrated version 3. LISFLOOD+GREEN simulates annual nutrient loads and provides a grid output. GREEN is set to represent changing nutrient sources in time so it is expected to provide more accurate interannual dynamics for longer simulation periods. However, it does not simulate sediments.

The datasets are given in NetCDF (.nc), CSV (.csv) format, text file (.txt) and shapefile formats, and are stored on both the shared project Google Drive and the shared project folder on the Open Science Framework (OSF) platform. Metadata files are also stored in addition to the datasets, and metadata are described in this document in detail.

Data can be accessed via the following links:

E-HYPE

- https://osf.io/pr9xh/?view_only=0a7d818627824f15954307eb2cd2d158

LISFLOOD: GREEN

- https://drive.google.com/drive/folders/1QGBycR2wB8UCkiug3R6h-ydSeMq8ueUO?usp=drive_link

Datasets follow the general guidelines laid out under deliverable **D1.1**, the project’s Data Management Plan, which is publicly available.

Table 1. General overview of the simulated variables at coastal outlets

Model	E-HYPE	LISFLOOD+GREEN
Model purpose within the FOCCUS project	Assess land to sea water discharge, sediment and nutrient pollution in historical periods	Assess land to sea water discharge and nutrient pollution in historical periods
Delivery variables	Streamflow (m ³ /s), concentrations and loads of nitrogen N (organic, inorganic, total), phosphorus P (soluble, particulate, total), and sediments (total suspended solids) (mg/l and kg/d)	Streamflow (m ³ /s), total N and P estimated loads (tonN/yr), N and P concentrations at basin outlets (mg/l)
Delivery period	2000-2019	1990-2021
Time-step	daily	annual*

*Historic daily LISFLOOD EFASv5 River discharge (1992-2025) can be accessed on CEMS Early Warning DataStore:

<https://ewds.climate.copernicus.eu/datasets/efas-historical?tab=download>

2. SMHI’s Freshwater Model, E-HYPE

2.1 Introduction to E-HYPE

The Hydrological Predictions for the Environment (HYPE, Lindström et al., 2010) model is an open-source, physically-based, semi-distributed model developed by SMHI to simulate water quantity and quality (SMHI, 2023). The model runs on daily time-step, taking into account main nutrient and sediment sources obtained from open-source datasets (see deliverable **D4.2**).

The purpose of the E-HYPE model in the FOCCUS project is to supply coastal applications with daily streamflow, nutrient and sediment concentration at the coastal outlets. E-HYPE estimates these daily freshwater inflows for 5302 ungauged coastal outlets based on physically based semi-distributed processes representation.

The limitations of the freshwater inflows produced by the E-HYPE version 4.3 model are as follows:

- nutrient sources (point source discharges, fertilizer application rates, etc.) are constant over the provided time period,

- some outlet points are symbolic in nature, e.g. a runoff from a smaller catchment along the coastline can reach the coastal waters in a dispersed way along the coastal line (see 2.2 Supporting illustrations),
- model outputs represent only freshwater fluxes without any consideration of actual estuarine processes (tides, mixing etc.).

Please see the deliverable **D4.2** for detailed model description, input data and calibration routine.

2.2 Metadata

The following files are shared with partners of the project FOCCUS. The results are preliminary and should not be shared outside of the project. The results are from E-HYPE version 4.2.2 (EH4) executed with HYPE code v.5.23.0. for the time period 2000-2019. Nutrient sources represent the year 2010.

Outlet point description:

"EH4_coastal_outlets.txt" file describes metadata for EH4 outlet points discharging into coasts. Smaller rivers and creeks along the coastline may be aggregated into one catchment with one virtual outlet point that does not represent any particular river.

SUBID: EH4 catchment identification number

HAROID: EH4 basin identification number

MAINDOWN: catchment identification number of a downstream catchment, 0 for coasts

POURX: longitude of the outlet point

POURY: latitude of the outlet point

TARGETX: longitude of the catchment target point

TARGETY: latitude of the catchment target point

CENTERX: longitude of the catchment centroid

CENTERY: latitude of the catchment centroid

AREA: catchment area, m²

UPAREA: upstream area draining to the catchment, m²

TOTAREA: total area contributing to the outlet point, m²

Data description:

Daily time series of EH4 outputs are provided for each coastal outlet (identified by "SUBID") in two formats, netcdf (folder "nc" on OSF) and plain text files (folder "txt" on FOCCUS Google Drive). The following variables are provided:

cout: freshwater discharge, m³/s

ccin: simulated concentration of inorganic nitrogen, ug/l

ccon: simulated concentration of organic nitrogen, ug/l

ccfn: simulated concentration of total nitrogen, ug/l

ccsp: simulated concentration of soluble (reactive) phosphorus, ug/l

ccpp: simulated concentration of particulate phosphorus, ug/l

ccfp: simulated concentration of total phosphorus, ug/l

ccst: simulated concentration of total suspended solids, mg/l

The netCDF datasets and metadata *.txt files are accessible under the FOCCUS WP4/5 page under the FOCCUS project located in the Open Science Framework (OSF) Platform. Access can be requested at the following link, which will be shared with the project partners:

https://osf.io/pr9xh/?view_only=0a7d818627824f15954307eb2cd2d158

2.3 Supporting illustrations

EH4 only calculates inputs from land and their transport through freshwater systems. Typically, the most downstream point is represented by a river outlet point delivering freshwater and related constituents to the coastal area from the upstream contributing areas. There are also areas e.g. along an estuary that are contributing directly to the estuary without collecting in one single river before reaching the coast but rather reaching the estuary in a dispersed way along the coastal line. Here are a couple illustrations.

Example 1: in both locations at the figure below, the orange points have a larger drainage area than the dark red points and represent the main river inflow. The red points represent outlets from basins draining directly to the estuary. The red points here represent virtual outlet points for coastal basins summarizing freshwater inflows along the corresponding (green) coastal lines. Note the upper dark red point – there the drainage area contributes to both estuaries shown on the map. In the coastal model, the modeler needs to make a decision on how the inputs will be allocated along the coastline.

Example 2: the orange point is located in the middle of the estuary but it represents a combined freshwater inflow from land to the estuary through a major river as well as part of the directly connected area that is within the same catchment. It does not represent actual flows or concentrations at the coordinates where the point is located. The darker red points represent virtual outlet points for coastal basins summarizing freshwater inflows along the corresponding (green) coastal lines.

3. JRC Freshwater modelling approach

3.1 Introduction to LISFLOOD & GREEN

The JRC freshwater modelling approach combines two independent models that are coupled offline to estimate riverine inputs (water discharge and nutrient loads) to the seas. The purpose of the model system is to provide a framework that links land to sea, and enable assessing impacts of EU environmental policy on all waters (freshwaters and marine waters). The two models represent the freshwater part in the JRC land-to-sea [Blue2 framework](#) that is developed to support the EU environmental policy on fresh and marine waters (Grizzetti et al., 2021; Friedland et al., 2021; Piroddi et al. 2021, Macias et al., 2024). The modelling suite comprises the hydrological model LISFLOOD coupled with the conceptual model GREEN. A detailed description of the

two models is provided in deliverable **D4.2**. Herein only a brief description of historic simulation of GREEN is given for the purposes of the FOCCUS project.

LISFLOOD is a process-based hydrological model that simulates water discharge at 6 hours time step intervals. The model covers the European continent and is spatially distributed at an 1 arcmin grid (approximately 1.5 km). LISFLOOD model is open source and a full description of the model can be found in [online documentation](#). LISFLOOD has been applied for flood prevention, river regulation, drought and soil moisture assessment, and for evaluating the impacts of climate and land-use changes on water resources. Currently the model informs the European Flood Awareness System (EFAS) and the Global Flood Awareness System (GLOFAS) services of the [Copernicus Emergency Management System](#) (EMS). LISFLOOD river discharge output for the latest calibration (version 4.3.1; status June 2024) from 1991 to 2024 is available [online](#).

GREEN is a conceptual model that simulates annual nutrient loads (total nitrogen TN and total phosphorus TP, in t/y) for the European continent. The model outputs are provided at the scale of its spatial units (subcatchments of approximate 7 km² mean area), and at the basin outlets. The GREEN outputs provided to the FOCCUS project cover the period 1990 to 2021 and consider changes in nutrient sources from the inception of the EU Urban WasteWater Treatment Directive and the Nitrate Directives to nowadays. A full description of model assumptions, input datasets, and changes in nutrient fluxes during this period is given in Vigiak et al. (2023).

For the purpose of the FOCCUS project, model outputs included here comprise annual discharges and annual loads of total nitrogen and total phosphorus for coastal outlets during 1990-2021. The main limitations of the model system for coastal application are

1. the system builds on models that were originally developed independently and to serve different purposes, thus the system inherited historical inconsistencies in spatial and temporal resolutions and in input data;
2. the models are coupled offline, which hampers propagation of assessment of uncertainties, and
3. the freshwater system of LISFLOOD and Green, which is mainly developed for considering water quantity and nutrient pollution, may not cover all needs that could be useful for analysis of coastal environments. For example, it is still missing a module for water temperature and suspended sediment modelling.

3.2 Metadata

Annual outputs of GREEN model simulation (April 2024 calibration - Output Version nr.59) for the historic conditions of Europe for 1990-2021 (HYST_1990_2021) was provided by JRC to the FOCCUS project. Datasets are provided as text file (.csv format), with accompanying metadata in .txt format and GIS greenBasin shapefiles. Files were uploaded on FOCCUS project Google Drive on on 2024-06-27 : [https://drive.google.com/drive/folders/1QGBycR2wB8UCkiug3R6h-ydSeMq8ueUO?usp=drive link](https://drive.google.com/drive/folders/1QGBycR2wB8UCkiug3R6h-ydSeMq8ueUO?usp=drive_link).

These data will be published and permanently stored in the JRC Data Catalogue in the Water Pressure Indicators collection (<https://data.jrc.ec.europa.eu/collection/wpi>) in Summer 2025 - the exact reference will be provided as soon as published.

HydroID is the key to link basin output location (seaOutlet.csv) and GREEN model results (files .CSV for N and P).

(Please note that BasinID could be also used given that BasinID is also present in GREEN model result files.)

BasinID is the key to link basin output location (seaOutlet.csv) and GREEN model river basins (greenBasin shapefile).

Variables for nitrogen file:

[VersionNr] --> Green output version id

[HydroID] --> HydroEurasiaV23 catchment ID

[BasinID] --> HydroEurasiaV23 river basin ID

[NextDownID]

[Shreve]

[YearValue] --> year

[CatchLoad] --> estimated load at basin outlet (tonN/yr)

[DischargeM3s] --> estimated water flow at basin outlet from model LISFLOOD (annual mean discharge in m³/s)

[ConcNmg/l] --> estimated concentration basin outlet (mgN/l)

Variables for phosphorus file:

[VersionNr] --> Green output version id

[HydroID] --> HydroEurasiaV23 catchment ID

[BasinID] --> HydroEurasiaV23 river basin ID

[NextDownID]

[Shreve]

[YearValue] --> year

[CatchLoad] --> estimated load at basin outlet (tonP/yr)

[DischargeM3s] --> estimated water flow at basin outlet from model LISFLOOD (annual mean discharge, in m³/s)

[ConcPmg/l] --> estimated concentration basin outlet (mgP/l)

3.3 Notes on LISFLOOD-GREEN output usage

The JRC LISFLOOD-GREEN dataset shared in FOCCUS Google Drive contains mean water discharge for 1990-2021 at Basin outlets. These mean annual river discharge values come from a LISFLOOD configuration that was created for policy scenario analysis as part of Blue2 framework and does not correspond to the LISFLOOD simulations that are used in Copernicus services.

For best representation of water discharge at the river outlets at daily timescale, a direct retrieval of data from online Copernicus repository (<https://ewds.climate.copernicus.eu/datasets/efas-historical?tab=download>) is recommended. Conversely, for analysis on long time series in combination with nutrient loads of GREEN, the dataset provided in FOCCUS Google Drive is recommended.

GREEN annual loads and mean annual concentrations of nutrients to sea can be used to assess biogeochemical conditions in transitional, coastal, and marine waters. Examples of such analysis conducted within the JRC Blue2 framework can be found in Friedland et al. 2021, Piroddi et al. 2021 and Macias et al. 2024). Since these outputs are total nitrogen and total phosphorus at annual scale, further adjustments to consider nutrient chemical species and intra-annual variability may be required. Within the FOCCUS project, procedures to account for these will be further explored.

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